

EAA 2019

25 years

Beyond paradigms

BERN
4 - 7 September

Abstract Book

Beyond paradigms

HOW TO READ THE ABSTRACT BOOK

The Abstract Book is ordered by session numbers which were allocated during the session submission (i.e., the number sequence is discontinuous).

Author's affiliation is stated in brackets following the author's name; where authors share the same affiliation, it is only stated once.

Index of Authors includes all session organisers and only the main authors of contributions.

Please note that names, titles and affiliations are reproduced as submitted by the session organisers and/or authors. Language and wording of titles and abstracts are not revised.

25th EAA Annual Meeting (Bern, 2019) – Abstract Book

Technical editing: Kateřina Kleinová (EAA)

Design and layout: Susanna Kaufmann

ISBN: 978-80-907270-6-9

European Association of Archaeologists

Bern, August 2019

© European Association of Archaeologists, 2019

Contents ...

16	THE MATERIALITY OF HIGH ALTITUDES AND HIGH LATITUDES.....	11
17	MEDIEVAL ARCHAEOLOGY IN EUROPE TODAY.....	12
27	ARCHAEOLOGICAL PERSPECTIVES ON REFORM AND REVOLUTION: MATERIAL CULTURE IN THE LONG ELEVENTH CENTURY.....	12
39	RECENT ARCHAEOLOGICAL INVESTIGATION IN INHABITED MEDIEVAL RURAL SETTLEMENTS: NEW PERSPECTIVES FROM HISTORIC COMMUNITIES PAST AND PRESENT.....	17
43	THE POLITICAL GEOGRAPHY OF WESTERN ANATOLIA IN THE LBA, AND THE REGION'S INTERACTION WITH ITS NEIGHBOURS, IN PARTICULAR THE BALKAN.....	22
46	CENTRAL MEDITERRANEAN PREHISTORY AT THE EAA25 TURN: RESEARCH ADVANCES AND NEW DIRECTIONS.....	27
55	FORGOTTEN CASTLE LANDSCAPES: CONNECTING RESEARCH AND HERITAGE, MONUMENTS AND LANDSCAPES.....	33
57	FROM LOCAL TO GLOBAL. CURRENT PERSPECTIVES ON EDUCATION AND CULTURAL HERITAGE.....	37
60	BEYOND "FOUNDER CROPS": NEW INSIGHTS INTO UNDERSTUDIED FOOD PLANT RESOURCES.....	39
66	PROFESSIONAL COMMUNICATION OF ARCHAEOLOGICAL RESEARCH - TRAININGS AND OWNED MEDIA.....	42
68	15 YEARS AFTER MERRIMAN - PUBLIC ARCHAEOLOGY: LOOKING BACK AND THINKING ABOUT THE FUTURE.....	44
69	POPULISM, IDENTITY POLITICS AND THE ARCHAEOLOGY OF EUROPE.....	47
73	MESSY METHODS: HERITAGE STUDIES AND THE QUEST FOR MULTI-METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES.....	50
74	DE-COLONISATION AT EAA 25 YEARS ON: THE SOCIAL-ECONOMIC CONTRIBUTION OF CULTURAL HERITAGE CONSERVATION.....	54
76	SYSTEMIC APPROACHES TO JUVENILE FUNERARY RITUALS. ATYPICAL, DEVIANT OR NORMATIVE? GOING BEYOND PARADIGMS.....	56
81	FROM MICRO- TO MACROSCALE: IT'S ALL A MATTER OF PERSPECTIVE.....	65
85	TRACKING NEOLITHISATION PROCESSES ON BOTH SIDES OF THE SINAI: A BRIDGE BETWEEN THE NEAR EAST AND NORTHEASTERN AFRICA.....	71
88	FUNERARY PRACTICES AT ÇATALHÖYÜK AND IN THE NEOLITHIC NEAR EAST: MULTIDISCIPLINARY PERSPECTIVES.....	75
90	'MASSIVE MIGRATIONS'? MULTISCALAR AND MULTIDISCIPLINARY APPROACHES TO PREHISTORIC MIGRATIONS AND MOBILITY IN EUROPE.....	79
91	BIOARCHAEOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO UNDERSTANDING THE LONG-TERM DEVELOPMENT OF MOUNTAIN SOCIETIES.....	83
94	WORKING WITH CERAMICS IN THE 21ST CENTURY.....	87
95	CPAA SESSION: ORGANISING ARCHAEOLOGISTS – ARCHAEOLOGICAL ASSOCIATIONS OF EUROPE.....	93
97	MOTHERHOOD IN (PRE-)HISTORY FROM A COMBINED BIO-ARCHAEOLOGICAL AND SOCIAL PERSPECTIVE.....	96
107	LIVING (WORLD) HERITAGE CITIES. INSIGHTS FROM ARCHAEOLOGY AND HISTORY, GEOGRAPHY AND SOCIAL SCIENCES, AND PLANNING AND DESIGN.....	99
109	GETTING INTO SHAPE: RECONSIDERING THE RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN PERCEPTION, SKILL, COGNITION AND MATERIALS IN THE DESIGN OF ANCIENT FIGURINES.....	103
111	DEVELOPMENT OF HERITAGE MANAGEMENT EDUCATION.....	108
114	ILLEGAL OBTAINING AND TRADE OF ARCHAEOLOGICAL ARTEFACTS: STATUS QUO AND COUNTERACTION.....	108
121	CURRENT RESEARCH AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF NATIONAL POST-MEDIEVAL ARCHAEOLOGIES OVER THE LAST 25 YEARS.....	110
125	COMMUNITIES, IDENTITIES, RITUALS. THE BRONZE/IRON AGE URNFIELDS AS A PAN-EUROPEAN PHENOMENON.....	114
128	BREAKING OLD PARADIGMS: THE ARCHAEOLOGY AND ETHNOARCHAEOLOGY OF PASTORALISM IN THE INNER AREAS OF THE MEDITERRANEAN BASIN.....	120
133	ANCIENT TEXTILE PRODUCTION FROM AN INTERDISCIPLINARY APPROACH: HUMANITIES AND NATURAL SCIENCES INTERWOVEN FOR OUR UNDERSTANDING OF TEXTILES.....	123
140	FURNISHED INTERIORS IN THE ANCIENT MEDITERRANEAN AND EGYPT.....	129
142	SO CLOSE, NO MATTER HOW FAR? SKETCHING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN WATER- AND LANDSCAPES ACROSS EUROPE.....	133
144	TOWARDS A SPATIAL DATA INFRASTRUCTURE FOR ARCHAEOLOGY.....	138
150	DECOLONISING SPACE.....	141
152	APPROACHING HEALTH STATUS, HEALTH CARE AND PEOPLE'S WELLBEING IN THE PAST FROM A DENTAL ANTHROPOLOGICAL PERSPECTIVE.....	144
155	HOUSEHOLD TEXTILES IN AND BEYOND VIKING AGE.....	148
156	CRAFTING FOR THE USER: THE INTERSECTION OF DAILY LIFE AND OBJECT-MAKING.....	150
157	AT THE FRINGE OF EARLY NEOLITHISATION – FROM THE COASTS TO THE MOUNTAINS.....	153
162	CULTURE CONTACTS IN THE WESTERN MEDITERRANEAN SEA DURING THE ROMAN AGE. POTTERY AS CULTURAL MARKER BETWEEN TRAFFICS AND LOCAL PRODUCTIONS.....	158

9 THE BALTS AND KIEVAN RUS'. NEW BALTIC CEMETERY OF THE 11TH CENTURY IN UKRAINE.

Author(s): Shiroukhov, Roman (Centre for Baltic and Scandinavian Archaeology - ZBSA) - Baranov, Vyacheslav - Ivakin, Vsevolod (Institute of Archaeology of National Academy of Science of Ukraine)

Presentation Format: Oral

Two years ago Ukrainian scientists found an early medieval cemetery, which will soon become one of the most important archaeological finds in post-soviet Ukrainian history.

Ostriv-1 cemetery is located on the low terrace of Ros' river approximately 100 km. south of Kiev. During 2017-2018 excavations of V.Ivakin and V.Baranov on 1000 square m. 53 inhumation graves with head orientation to the north were found. This kind of burial rite is untypical to the Christian Kievan Rus'. On the other hand, inhumations with the north orientation were characteristic first of all to the Baltic tribes of Semigallians, Selonians, Latgallians, Samogitians as well as to the Curonians (till the 11th century) and Prussians (since the 11th century). This type of burial rite is typical for some Gotlandic 11th century cemeteries and the early Piast Poland. Sambian peninsula Prussians inhumations with north orientation appear within the typical cremation cemeteries area, some of them with Kievan Rus' imported goods. It is important to stress that Sambian peninsula of the 11-12th centuries was the region of the huge Old Ruthenian imported goods concentration.

The most of grave goods of Ostriv-1 belong to the 11th century and are characteristic to the Prussians, Curonians, Scalvians and Semigallians. The penannular brooches from Ostriv-1 are unknown for Kiev Rus', but identical to these, found at Kaliningrad region and West Lithuanian cemeteries.

According to O. Kozak anthropological analysis, the first results of the skeletal remains study demonstrated that the paleopopulation of Ostriv-1 was young and had a low adaptation level, what could be characteristic for the first wave incomers.

At the initial stage of research, we can stress that population of Ostriv-1 consisted of East Baltic region incomers connected to the Jaroslaw the Wise migration and defence politics of the first half of the 11th century, mentioned in Nestor's Chronicle.

10 NORMANITAS IN SICILY

Author(s): Carver, Martin (University of York)

Presentation Format: Oral

The objective of this short paper is to review the impact of the Norman period in Sicily in terms of urban development, rural settlement, agriculture, trade - and demography as indicated by the cemeteries. The 'Norman period' may be defined as running from the first incursions of the Hautevilles in 1061/68, to the occupation of Palermo in 1091, to the creation of the kingdom of Roger II in 1130, to his death in 1154, to the death of Tancred in 1194. At this point Sicily became a dominion of the Hohenstaufen/Swabian regime. During the 150 years in question, the mid 11th to the late 12th century, the character of society and the economy changed in a set of subterranean rhythms that suggest that the policies of successive rulers were not necessarily the prime movers.

The project 'sictransit' sets out to assess the Norman impact on the Greek, Arab and Roman peoples of the island and the consequent achievements of the farmers, merchants and their families of mixed origins whose agency is suspected of being determinant. This paper will ask how far we can identify archaeological correlates that could be described as Normanitas and if so how they were modified by the conquered peoples.

Sictransit is an ERC project of the Universities of York, Rome Tor Vergata and Lecce

<http://sicilyintransition.org>

11 THE LANDSCAPE OF SKYE AND THE WESTERN ISLES IN THE VIKING AGE AND LATE NORSE PERIODS

Author(s): Ryder, Joseph (University of Bergen)

Presentation Format: Oral

The Norse period of Skye and the Western Isles of Scotland began in the late 8th century AD with the first Viking raids, and ends in the mid-13th century with the annexation of the islands from the Norwegian crown to the Scottish crown. This Norse period has traditionally been divided into the Viking Age (790-1087 AD) and the Late Norse period (1087-1266 AD), on the basis of the historical evidence that shows the creation of the Kingdom of the Isles from 1087 AD. The archaeological material of the period between 950-1150 AD shows dramatic changes: the foundations of Norse longhouses go from post and turf built to stone built, Norse pagan burials cease, and many of the pre-Norse monumental structures of the islands were likely reoccupied. Moreover, the islands themselves were integrated into the Kingdom of the Isles, shifting their geopolitical influence from the Jarldom of Orkney to the Isle of Man in the Irish Sea region, and Skye became the seat of the Skeabost diocese, under the authority of the archbishop of Trondheim. In this paper, I will examine the changes that occur in this period through a survey of the archaeological evidence, and take into consideration the role of religion and ethnicity within a landscape context. In this paper, I argue that ethnic, religion and social forces affected the landscape of Skye and the Western Isles during the Norse Period, with an emphasis on the mid-10th to mid-12th centuries.